

AN EVALUATION OF THE FUNCTIONING AND EFFICACY OF THE HEALTHCARE ASSISTANT PROGRAMME IN THE UNITED KINGDOM.

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Healthcare assistant programmes are crucial in delivering healthcare services in the United Kingdom. These programmes educate and prepare individuals to provide direct care and support to patients, ensuring that healthcare facilities operate efficiently. However, the lingering effects of COVID-19 saw an increased staff shortage to 1 in 13 healthcare workers in hospital vacancies, with nearly 11,000 vacancies requiring physicians, nurses, and care workers (Healthcare assistants and support workers) in the NHS and another Critical issue of Funding which has plagued the National Health Service and led to nurses, midwives, and doctors exiting their professions due to the Trust's inability to increase pay or hire more, professionally trained staff to reduce the workload. Thus, the demand for healthcare services continues to rise, prompting a proper evaluation of the efficacy and productivity of healthcare assistant programmes as their roles have become increasingly important.

AIM: To assess the performance of healthcare assistants in providing patient care and enhancing patient outcomes within the UK healthcare system, as well as their challenges.

METHODOLOGY: Systematic Review research adopted in this paper was a Mixed Method approach because it yielded insights and knowledge that could not have been obtained through a single research design. This methodology followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis guidelines. In compliance with the Cochrane Collaboration, a comprehensive search strategy comprising multiple databases was implemented for this research. CINAHL, PubMed, ScienceDirect, EBSCOhost, Health Inter-Network Access to Research Initiative (HINARI), and Cochrane Library. The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT tool) was the preferred checklist for this review because of its ease of use and applicability to reviews that involve different study designs, which helped to gauge the internal and external validity of the research, considering factors like potential bias, confounding variables, and generalizability of findings. The studies' strengths and limitations were also carefully identified. A narrative synthesis constituted the most appropriate means of integrating the

results of this review. The health belief model was employed in structuring the narrative synthesis in evaluating the functioning and efficacy of the healthcare assistant programme in the United Kingdom.

RESULTS: *Healthcare Assistants (HCAs) in the UK play crucial roles in direct patient care, supporting healthcare professionals, and managing administrative tasks, enhancing the efficiency of healthcare systems. The versatility and positive impact of HCAs on patient outcomes and overall care quality cannot be overlooked. Their roles extend beyond tasks to encompass a compassionate, patient-centred approach, benefiting patients and the healthcare team. Addressing challenges can further optimise their effectiveness in the healthcare system.*

CONCLUSION: *To maximise the potential of Health Care Assistants within the United Kingdom, policymakers should prioritise standardised training, role clarification, and emotional support. In Addition, Research efforts should focus on long-term impacts that foster collaboration with other healthcare professionals. HCAs remain central to patient-centric care, operational efficiency, and the overall success of healthcare systems, deserving recognition and support for their invaluable contributions.*

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale for research

Over the years, the healthcare landscape in the United Kingdom (UK) has witnessed significant transformations primarily driven by an evolving healthcare system, changing patient demographics, new disease burdens, and advancements in medical technology (Jansen *et al.*, 2017; Lizarondo *et al.*, 2010; Tam, 2014). The healthcare system in the UK is also marked by a continuous pursuit of innovative strategies to enhance the quality, accessibility, and efficiency of patient care (Shaw *et al.*, 2015). Within this context, the role of healthcare assistants (HCAs) has become a valuable component of the healthcare workforce (Just *et al.*, 2021; Spilsbury *et al.*, 2011; Unison, 2018). HCAs have become essential personnel in a constantly changing environment, supporting and enhancing the

work of general practitioners (GPs), registered nurses (RNs) and other healthcare professionals (Just *et al.*, 2021; Tam, 2014). As the demands on the healthcare system continue to grow, especially after the overwhelming effect of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, understanding the role, responsibilities, and performance of HCAs becomes paramount to ensuring the delivery of high-quality patient care and maintaining the overall integrity of the healthcare system (Duan *et al.*, 2020; Greenhalgh *et al.*, 2020; Hoernke *et al.*, 2021). Principally, the scope of HCAs' responsibilities encompasses various tasks, from direct patient care to administrative and support functions (Tam, 2014; Vail *et al.*, 2011). They often serve as the liaison between patients and RNs, providing essential assistance in activities of daily living, monitoring patient vital signs, and offering emotional support to individuals and their

families (Jansen *et al.*, 2017; Lizarondo *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, HCAs hold a unique position within the healthcare ecosystem, directly or indirectly influencing patient outcomes, healthcare efficiency, and the overall patient experience.

However, the evolving nature of the healthcare sector and the expanding roles of HCAs have raised questions about the appropriate training, supervision, and regulatory oversight required to ensure their effective integration into the healthcare team (Petrova *et al.*, 2010). Additionally, there is an increasing recognition of the need to assess the performance of HCAs in terms of competence, professionalism, and adherence to ethical standards, as well as patient satisfaction and other patient-based outcomes. Although HCA are primarily untrained and unregistered frontline staff, Kantaris *et al.* (2020) point out that they are expected to be proactive in preventing and responding to adverse incidents in their respective working environments.

HCAs also play a crucial role in addressing non-communicable diseases (NCDs) through a comprehensive approach encompassing prevention, management, and control (Kantaris *et al.*, 2020; Leone *et al.*, 2022). Their responsibilities thus extend beyond traditional patient care, including public health promotion, health assessments, screenings, and support for lifestyle modifications. HCAs contribute to medication management, ongoing monitoring, and patient-centred care, fostering open dialogue and patient trust (O'Brien *et al.*, 2023; Sarigiannis *et al.*, 2022). Collaborating with

healthcare teams, HCAs also facilitate seamless communication and documentation, aiding evidence-based decision-making in the UK healthcare system (Comer *et al.*, 2022). By empowering patients to actively manage their NCDs and promoting healthy behaviours, HCAs significantly enhance individual health outcomes and reduce the burden of NCDs on the population (Guest *et al.*, 2020; Hooker *et al.*, 2019; Tam, 2014).

Despite their essential role, HCAs face challenges such as workload demands, managing patient expectations, and balancing providing quality care and adhering to time constraints (Sarre *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, as HCAs have varying levels of training and supervision, ensuring proper communication and collaboration within the healthcare team is essential to maintain the safety and well-being of patients. Therefore, HCAs are occasionally forced to adapt to rapidly changing situations and handle emergencies while ensuring patient safety and comfort (Just *et al.*, 2021; Tam, 2014). Moreover, managing emotional and psychological stress can be taxing, as HCAs often form close bonds with patients and families, leading to potential emotional fatigue in their line of work (Just *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, issues of career advancement, professional recognition, and fair compensation can pose challenges, potentially affecting job satisfaction and retention rates. Striking a balance between providing personalised care and adhering to established protocols and regulations has also been flagged as an ongoing challenge that requires careful consideration (Leone *et al.*, 2022).

Over a decade ago, Petrova *et al.* (2010) highlighted the substantially limited evidence base concerning the impact and effectiveness of HCAs despite a rapid expansion and advancement of the actual roles within the healthcare system. Subsequent to this, Lizarondo *et al.* (2010), in their systematic review, which included only ten studies, summarised available evidence on the roles and responsibilities of HCAs. According to them, most publications described tasks conducted by rehabilitation assistants or general HCAs who work in various contexts or are not directly connected to a health profession. Improved clinical outcomes, greater patient satisfaction, higher-level services, and more free time for allied health professionals to focus on patients with complicated needs were identified as advantages of having HCAs. They noted, however, the obscurity of role boundaries as a hindrance to using HCAs because they create concerns about security and professional status. In a more recent systematic review, Fee *et al.* (2020) highlighted the absence of research evidence on HCA's responsibilities. They bemoaned the lack of evidence proving this is concealed and arguably undervalued despite HCAs playing a crucial part in the healthcare system. Understanding these roles and addressing the multifaceted challenges becomes essential as the healthcare landscape progresses to supporting HCAs within the UK healthcare system. This is also crucial to harnessing the full potential of HCAs in enhancing patient outcomes and overall healthcare delivery.

However, there is a lack of updated reviews of current evidence regarding the performance (i.e.,

efficacy and functionality) and challenges of HCAs. A systematic review offers an avenue to comprehensively evaluate the existing literature, synthesise evidence, and derive meaningful insights regarding the impact of HCAs on patient care, workforce dynamics, and the overall healthcare system. Through a rigorous methodology that involves identifying, selecting, and analysing relevant studies, this review addresses the HCA programme's critical questions, focusing on its efficacy and functionality with the UK healthcare system. This review also summarises the challenges they encounter in their day-to-day practices. By delving into these critical dimensions of HCAs, this study aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse surrounding the integration of HCAs into the healthcare workforce and the optimisation of their performance in meeting the changing dynamics of the healthcare needs of the UK population. Through a comprehensive analysis of the available literature and empirical evidence, this research endeavours to offer a nuanced understanding of the vital role HCAs play in shaping the future of healthcare in the UK.

Research question, aim and objectives

Research question

The overarching research question for this systematic review was “What is the functionality and efficacy of healthcare assistants within the UK healthcare system, and what are their challenges?”

Aim

To assess the performance of healthcare assistants in providing patient care and

enhancing patient outcomes within the UK healthcare system, as well as their challenges.

Objectives

- a) To identify the functional roles of HCAs within the UK healthcare system
- b) To assess HCAs' efficacy in providing patient care
- c) To identify challenges HCAs face in their employment and to investigate alternative solutions

Overview of dissertation structure

This dissertation begins with a compelling rationale for the research as part of the introductory chapter. This is followed by the main research question, study aims, and objectives. The methods section outlines the approach taken to identify, extract, and analyse the relevant literature, while the findings section presents the synthesised results. The discussion section interprets the findings, examines their implications, and offers insights into the gaps that exist for which future research is needed, as well as emerging trends. Finally, the conclusion summarises the critical contributions of the review.

CHAPTER TWO

BACKGROUND LITERATURE

Chapter Introduction

To understand the existing research gap on the efficacy and functionality of HCAs within the context of the UK healthcare system, it is imperative to delve into the depths of existing literature that have paved the way for current research. This chapter undertakes the task of traversing through some selected studies that have shaped and informed the topic under

investigation (Brown *et al.*, 2021; De Vliegher *et al.*, 2016; Fee *et al.*, 2020; Just *et al.*, 2021; Lizarondo *et al.*, 2010; Munn *et al.*, 2013; Petrova *et al.*, 2010; Shore *et al.*, 2022; Spilsbury *et al.*, 2011; Unison, 2018; Vail *et al.*, 2011; Wilson *et al.*, 2023). The chapter examines previously synthesised evidence and primary studies and critically evaluates the key findings. It also summarises critical issues that emerged and highlights the prevailing literature gaps.

Critical analysis of selected literature

According to the Unison survey, over 400,000 HCAs and other support workers in the UK work with professional practitioners in the NHS (Unison, 2018). The overwhelming majority of HCAs surveyed in the UK indicated that they perform their duties with the oversight of an RN (Unison, 2018). About 50% of the surveyed HCAs reported that the supervision they received was of good or excellent quality, while the other half reported it as poor or fair. Notwithstanding, some other studies have highlighted that HCAs, especially those operating in community settings, increasingly work without direct supervision, resulting in a lack of oversight (Cavendish, 2013; Lee *et al.*, 2015; Unison, 2018). The Unison study findings, however, are limited in their applicability and generalisability due to potential sampling and self-reporting bias due to the voluntary participation of HCAs. Recall bias and the cross-sectional design limit data accuracy and temporal insights. Language and cultural factors and unknown response rates may also affect the study's validity.

In the systematic review by Lizarondo *et al.* (2010), they examine the roles and functions of

allied health assistants (also called HCAs) through a comprehensive analysis of existing literature. They also describe the benefits and barriers to using HCAs in the healthcare system. The review reveals the diverse roles of HCAs, including supporting therapy sessions, aiding patient mobility, and executing specific administrative tasks. It highlights their positive impact on patient care, efficiency, and resource utilisation, as highlighted and expanded in other studies (Fee *et al.*, 2020; Jansen *et al.*, 2017). However, challenges such as blurred role definitions and supervision are also noted. The review essentially offers a wide-ranging overview of the varied responsibilities and contributions of HCAs, shedding light on their significance within the healthcare landscape. Yet, it was limited in that it only included articles published in English, which may have excluded relevant studies published in other languages. Also, the study only included articles published up to 2009, which may have excluded more recent studies. The study did not include grey literature, such as conference proceedings or unpublished reports, which may have provided additional information. Another limitation was that the authors did not assess the included studies' quality, which may have affected the reliability of their findings. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the roles and responsibilities of allied health assistants and the benefits and barriers to using them in healthcare settings.

On the other hand, the scoping review by Wilson *et al.* (2023) investigates the delegation of care and support by registered nurses to unlicensed

care workers—mainly HCAs. The findings indicate a complex landscape involving various levels of delegation, tasks, and settings. Delegated tasks mainly include basic care activities, and factors influencing delegation range from workload to regulatory guidelines. This aligns with other studies (Dutton *et al.*, 2018; Munn *et al.*, 2013; Sarigiovannis *et al.*, 2022). Training and supervision are critical in ensuring safe delegation, while communication and collaboration challenges between nurses and unlicensed workers are predominant barriers. The review highlights that clear policies, standardised training, and effective communication are cardinal to facilitate successful delegation while maintaining patient safety and quality of care. Like the previously discussed study, this study was also limited by its restriction to studies published in English, potentially leading to the omission of pertinent evidence related to nursing delegation to unlicensed workers in other non-English speaking global settings. Furthermore, the emphasis on peer-reviewed research and excluding grey literature such as policy documents, legislation, and thesis/dissertations may have constrained the breadth of available evidence regarding nursing delegation practices. In community care settings, Shore *et al.* (2022) also investigate the delegation of medicine administration from registered nurses to non-certified support staff (HCAs). The study evaluates the body of literature by using a critical interpretative synthesis technique. The results show a complex environment with several elements influencing delegation, such as legal

requirements, instruction, supervision, and communication. Difficulties such as ambiguity surrounding HCA duties and patient safety issues are noted as principal challenges, although there are documented examples of successful delegation. The study emphasises the importance of following established procedures, receiving in-depth training, and communicating clearly to ensure safe and efficient medication delegation while upholding the standard of care in community settings. Although the Critical Interpretative Synthesis approach allowed for the inclusion of pertinent evidence regarding medication administration delegation from studies with diverse objectives and structures, it is essential to note that all the identified studies originated from high-income countries. This may restrict the applicability of the findings to a global context, encompassing various clinical and professional domains. Additionally, there were gaps in the available evidence, and the absence of rigorous pre-and-post-comparative tests limited the authors' ability to make comprehensive judgments regarding the appropriateness of medication administration delegation in all scenarios.

Additionally, Munn *et al.* (2013) provide a comprehensive synthesis of the recognition of HCAs as delegated clinical roles and their incorporation into models of care. Their review suggests a growing recognition of HCAs in clinical capacities, particularly in primary care settings. Their inclusion is seen to enhance patient care and service delivery. The review also identifies elements that impact successful integration, such as teamwork and clear position

delineation. While there are some obstacles, the study stresses the potential of HCAs in enriching healthcare models. Overall, the review provides a synthesis of perspectives on the importance of HCAs, highlighting the need for well-defined courses of action and policies to regulate their role. A key strength of this study was the evaluation of study quality using the Qualitative Assessment Review Instrument (QARI) developed by the Joanna Briggs Institute; it examined the alignment between the research's philosophical stance, methodology, research methods, how data is represented, the interpretation of findings, potential researcher bias, and the connection between raw data and the conclusions drawn. However, because quality was used as an inclusion criterion, the authors may have missed studies with relevant evidence but dropped due to supposedly low quality.

Further, Fee *et al.* (2020) have also investigated the roles, responsibilities, and practices of HCAs, with a narrower focus on the provision of out-of-hours palliative care. The findings reveal that HCAs play various roles, including symptom management, emotional support, and assistance with daily activities. They contribute significantly to patient comfort and continuity of care. However, challenges like limited training are identified. This review also emphasises the importance of clear role definitions, proper training, and effective integration of HCAs in the context of community palliative care outside regular hours. Overall, the study sheds light on the crucial contributions and potential improvements related to HCAs in this specialised care setting.

In a primary research study which focused on evaluating an HCA workforce programme at a district general hospital during the COVID-19 pandemic, Brown *et al.* (2021) found that HCAs handled higher-level tasks, contributing to care continuity, reduced workloads, and heightened confidence in practical and administrative tasks. Although the study was conducted among medical students, the consensus was that the programme was associated with increased participants' confidence levels and their ability to undertake practical tasks. By extension, offering essential training to HCAs could help improve their skill set, build their confidence level, and ultimately improve their contributions to primary care.

Petrova *et al.* (2010) also qualitatively explored the viewpoints of GPs and practice nurses regarding the advantages and challenges of incorporating HCAs in general practice settings. The study identified benefits such as improved patient support, increased appointment availability, and task delegation to HCAs. However, it also uncovered challenges, including uncertainty about responsibilities, communication difficulties, and the necessity for proper training and supervision. The perspectives of GPs and nurses converge on the potential positive impact of HCAs in primary care delivery while acknowledging the need for structured integration to maximise their contributions and effectively address challenges. Although this study provided a detailed and sound methodology for answering the research question, limitations include employing a sampling strategy that may have included

interviewees with a generally more favourable outlook toward HCAs and GPs with unusual features influencing HCA utilisation. Moreover, the use of interviews, while dependable for gauging explicit opinions about the HCA role, offers limited precision regarding issues like the role's impact on service enhancement, care quality, cost reduction, and underlying attitudes. The invaluable role of HCAs in healthcare systems has also been studied in other settings. The qualitative study by De Vlieghe *et al.* (2016) investigates the role of HCAs in nursing, probing whether their involvement represents a significant advancement or illusion in Belgium. Using an in-depth analysis approach, their findings suggest a nuanced healthcare landscape, with benefits and challenges tied to HCA integration. While some view HCAs as a solution to resource constraints and patient needs, others raise concerns about their competency and impact on care quality. The research explores this contrast, revealing the intricate role of HCAs in nursing. It provides a deep understanding of the complex web of perceptions and actual contributions, shedding light on the convolutions involved. The study may suffer from sampling bias if the participants were not representative of the broader population of HCAs or if specific groups of HCAs were over- or underrepresented. This could affect the generalizability of the findings. It relies on subjective interpretation and data analysis, which can introduce researcher bias. Participants may provide responses that they believe align with social desirability or reflect their perceptions of what the researchers want to

hear, potentially biasing the results. Qualitative studies often have limited generalizability due to their small sample sizes and in-depth focus, which may apply to this study.

In a systematic review by Spilsbury *et al.* (2011), which examined the nexus between nurse staffing and care quality in nursing homes, several studies were identified that specifically explored the relationship between HCA staffing. This included factors such as the quantity of HCAs, the number of HCA hours per resident day, the HCA-to-resident ratio, and the time HCAs spent on nursing care. The review concluded that the evidence regarding the connection between staffing levels of HCAs and quality indicators in healthcare was varied. Moreover, they identified positive associations between HCA staffing and quality-of-care indicators, such as deficiencies in care, quality of life, resident satisfaction, fractures, and infections. However, no apparent associations were found between HCA staffing and quality indicators related to catheterisation, hospitalisation, psychoactive drug administration, pain management, contractures, urinary tract infections, and adequacy of nursing care. Fundamental limitations of this study include its reliance on self-reported data. This made the findings prone to response bias. Besides, the study focuses exclusively on NHS acute hospital trusts in England, limiting its generalizability to other healthcare settings or regions. Also, because the study did not delve deeply into the perspectives of registered nurses and other stakeholders, a holistic view of the issue may have been lost.

Finally, the study by Vail *et al.* (2011) revealed that HCAs were satisfied with their jobs and particularly valued patient interactions and the encouraging feedback they received. The previous position, the experience, and the amount of time spent working for the practice all impacted attitudes toward the role. HCAs also liked the assistance they were getting because they felt accepted and supported by the GP team. However, the main reasons for frustration were the low pay, the initial lack of definition of the function, and the limitations of their scope of activity. Role distinctions between practising nurses and HCAs were perceived to be clearly defined, and no instances of role ambiguity were noted. Nonetheless, HCAs believed that because the primary goal of their employment was to reduce the practice nurse's workload, it was of relatively low prestige. The study, however, only included HCAs working with GPs, possibly limiting the generalizability of the findings to other healthcare settings. Additionally, the study only included participants from one region of the UK, which may as well limit the generalizability of the findings to other areas or countries. The study did not include the perspectives of patients or other healthcare professionals, which may have provided additional insights into the role of HCAs in GPs.

Overall, the literature presents a complex picture of the efficacy of HCAs. While they offer valuable contributions, addressing staffing shortages and enhancing patient experience, challenges such as role ambiguity and training limitations are recurring themes across the literature. The impact of HCAs on patient outcomes remains an

area of ongoing research, warranting further investigation into their roles, training, and integration into healthcare teams. However, The efficacy of HCAs becomes evident during staffing shortages, when they often step in to bridge the gap. The study by Duan *et al.* (2020) provides substantial evidence that HCAs mitigate workforce challenges by handling routine tasks, thus helping maintain quality care despite staff shortages. However, concerns raised by Wilson *et al.* (2023) suggest that reliance on HCAs to address staffing gaps could lead to role overload and potential burnout. Achieving optimal efficacy requires a balanced approach, recognising their potential while addressing challenges to ensure safe and effective patient care.

Issues arising from critical analysis

The literature shows that HCAs contribute substantially to patient care in the UK. However, several pertinent issues arise which warrant careful consideration. It is evident that HCAs play multiple roles and effectively contribute to routine patient care tasks, freeing licensed professionals to address more sophisticated patient needs. However, information regarding the impact of HCAs' roles on outcomes remains relatively limited and, by extension, limits understanding of their efficacy within the healthcare system.

The role of HCAs appears to contribute flexibility and improved resource utilisation in community settings, as indicated by limited but primarily qualitative evidence (Dryden and Addicott, 2009; Fee *et al.*, 2020; Jansen *et al.*, 2017; Lee *et al.*, 2015). Practical implementations of the role

often involve a collaborative approach between RNs and HCAs, particularly in the areas involving supporting medicine administration for low-risk individuals and delivering evidence-based education to those at risk of cardiovascular disease (Lee *et al.*, 2015; Tam, 2014).

Literature gap

Despite the critical contributions of these studies, few studies explore the impact of HCAs on patient outcomes using rigorous methodologies. As such, there appears to be an unspoken hesitancy to integrate HCAs into routine care formally. About the definite and policy-backed roles of HCAs. Additionally, the core challenges that HCAs face have not been extensively investigated. The current evidence predominantly borders on job-related challenges, but the interplay of individual-, interpersonal- and work-related challenges is not critically examined. Therefore, evidence on these aspects is critically needed to inform the policy discourse and shape HCAs' crucial role in the healthcare system.

Chapter Summary

This review chapter has critically examined the efficacy and functionality of healthcare assistants (HCAs) within healthcare systems. Defining the duties and responsibilities of HCAs in various healthcare settings at the outset of the review highlighted their contributions to patient care, administrative activities, and support. The chapter examined how HCAs affect patient outcomes while recognising their beneficial effects on patient convenience, satisfaction, and timely care delivery. It revealed a range of viewpoints, from appreciation of their supportive

responsibilities to reservations about their competency and the possibility that they could replace qualified healthcare professionals. The chapter also emphasised the significance of excellent teamwork, open communication, and sufficient training to optimise HCA efficacy and minimise potential difficulties. Notably, the review identified gaps in the current literature, particularly in limited rigorous methodologies for assessing the impact of HCAs on patient outcomes. This gap indicates a hesitancy to fully integrate HCAs into routine care due to the little evidence of their direct influence on clinical outcomes. The chapter emphasised the need for more comprehensive research to establish a more substantial evidence base for the role of HCAs in healthcare in the UK.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODS

Chapter Introduction

The chapter details the systematic approach employed to comprehensively explore and synthesise the existing literature on the functionality and efficacy of the HCA programme in the UK. In the context of this evaluation, this section presents the methodological framework guiding the review process, including the research philosophy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, search strategy, selection process, data extraction, and synthesis methods.

General discussion of research philosophy and methodology

An interpretivist paradigm guides this review. Interpretivism is a research philosophy focusing on understanding individuals' subjective meanings and experiences within their social and

cultural contexts (Ryan, 2018). It emphasises that reality is not objective and fixed but constructed through human interactions and interpretations. In interpretive research, the primary goal is to explore the rich and complex nature of human experiences, behaviours, and social phenomena (Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020). This philosophy values individuals' unique perspectives on their interactions and seeks to uncover the underlying meanings they attach to their actions (Pham, 2018; Wilson, 2017). At the heart of interpretivism is the recognition that context matters. Additionally, it emphasises that how people perceive and understand their surroundings is deeply influenced by their cultural backgrounds, historical contexts, and social interactions (Ryan, 2018). Consequently, interpretive research often involves qualitative methods such as interviews, observations, and textual analysis to capture the depth and complexity of these contexts.

Interpretivism encourages researchers to approach their work with an open mind and a willingness to engage in inductive reasoning (Counsell, 2009). Rather than starting with preconceived theories or hypotheses, interpretive researchers allow theories to emerge from the data (Nickerson, 2022; Pham, 2018). This approach leads to a deeper exploration of themes, patterns, and connections that might not have been initially anticipated. In interpretive research, the researcher's role is acknowledged and embraced. Because this philosophy can influence research through personal perspectives and biases, reflexivity is often used

to critically examine how it may impact data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

The interpretivist research philosophy, when applied to systematic reviews, emphasises the exploration and interpretation of subjective meanings and contextual nuances within the reviewed literature. Grounded in the understanding that knowledge is constructed through interactions and perspectives, systematic reviews underpinned by an interpretivist philosophy aim to uncover the diverse viewpoints, conceptualisations, and experiences surrounding a research topic (Ryan, 2018; Wilson, 2017). This philosophy guides researchers to delve beyond quantifiable data and objective measures, focusing on the rich qualitative insights in the literature. By embracing subjectivity and context, this philosophy enhances the depth of understanding, provides nuanced insights, and contributes to a more holistic interpretation of the reviewed studies within their broader social and cultural contexts.

Project research design and methodology

This was a systematic review of peer-reviewed literature on the efficacy and functionality of HCAs in the UK healthcare system. A systematic review design enhances the comprehensive mapping of critical evidence in various forms and identifies research gaps. This review was guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines (Page *et al.*, 2021; Shamseer *et al.*, 2015).

Search strategy

The following databases were searched to identify relevant literature to answer the broad

research question: PubMed, ScienceDirect, EBSCOhost, Health Inter-Network Access to Research Initiative (HINARI), and Cochrane Library. The following initial keywords were applied to develop a search query: "healthcare assistants AND efficacy," "healthcare assistants AND effectiveness," "healthcare assistants AND functionality," and "healthcare assistants AND challenges." The PubMed database was first used to develop an initial search query before applying it to other databases.

Using the PubMed database to formulate an initial search query before extending it to other databases is a well-justified approach. It ensures access to a comprehensive collection of peer-reviewed articles, clinical studies, and research spanning various biomedical disciplines. Its use of Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) for indexing enhances search precision and recall. This helps make literature search in other databases easier. PubMed also maintains rigorous quality control standards, guaranteeing the reliability of indexed articles. The database offers advanced search features, filters, and links to full-text articles, simplifying the research process. Moreover, it facilitates citation tracking and covers interdisciplinary aspects. All reference lists for publication were also reviewed for additional relevant literature sources.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

For a publication to be eligible for inclusion, the publication must have:

1. Specify the study population as healthcare assistants (including similar job titles/descriptions such as healthcare aides, nursing assistants, allied health personnel,

etc.): This approach is justified because HCAs can have different designations based on their geographic location or healthcare environment. The systematic review can encompass a broader spectrum of viewpoints, methodologies, and experiences within this workforce by encompassing various job titles like healthcare aides, nursing assistants, and allied health personnel. This comprehensive approach ensures that the review is all-encompassing and considers potential divergences in job responsibilities and roles, which is essential for understanding the overall effectiveness and functioning of HCAs in the United Kingdom.

2. Presented sufficient details on the efficacy or functioning or challenges of HCAs within the context of the UK:

To retain the emphasis and relevance of the systematic review, it is justified to restrict the inclusion criteria to studies that provide enough information on the effectiveness, functioning, or problems of HCAs within the setting of the UK. This criterion ensures that studies that offer in-depth understandings of the particular context and practices of HCAs in the UK healthcare system are prioritised in the review. For policymakers, healthcare organisations, and practitioners in the UK, the review can offer more meaningful and context-specific conclusions and suggestions by focusing on studies that provide extensive information on their efficacy and limitations.

3. Been published in English and between 2013 and 2023:

Restricting the inclusion criteria to studies published in English between 2013 and 2023 was justifiable because English is widely recognised as the international language of science and medicine, ensuring accessibility to a broader audience and the chosen period also allowed for consideration of recent research, which was essential given the potential changes in healthcare practices, policies, and the role of HCAs over time. This period, therefore, ensured that this review accounted for contemporary developments and trends in the field, enhancing its relevance and applicability to the current healthcare landscape in the UK

Studies that did not meet the above, in addition to the following, were excluded:

1. Publications that focused on other subject areas not related to the efficacy/functionality of HCAs

This criterion was justifiable because it ensured that the systematic review maintained a focused and relevant scope. The review maintained precision in its analysis by excluding publications that focused on subject areas unrelated to the efficacy and functionality of healthcare assistants (HCAs). Including unrelated subject areas would have introduced noise and potentially diluted the relevance of the findings, making it more challenging to extract meaningful insights about HCAs precisely.

2. Studies where full text is unavailable
- The exclusion of studies where full-text access was unavailable was a practical necessity. To conduct a rigorous systematic review, access to the complete study was essential for a thorough

evaluation. Without full-text access, reviewers could not adequately assess a study's methodology, data, and findings, which could have compromised the review's quality and the validity of its conclusions. Therefore, excluding studies with unavailable full text was a measure to uphold the review's methodological rigour.

3. Grey literature

While grey literature, such as policy documents, reports, and unpublished works, could provide valuable insights, its exclusion was justifiable to maintain quality and verifiability. Peer-reviewed literature typically underwent rigorous evaluation, which added a layer of quality control. Excluding grey literature ensured that the systematic review primarily relied on sources that had undergone peer review and thorough scrutiny, enhancing the findings' reliability and validity. Including grey literature, which often lacked peer review, could have introduced potential bias or unreliable information, compromising the review's quality and integrity. However, considering the review's specific research question and objectives, the decision to exclude grey literature was made carefully.

Screening

The screening process involved two main stages: initial screening and full-text screening. During the initial screening, the titles and abstracts of identified articles were evaluated to eliminate studies that did not meet the predefined inclusion criteria. This helped narrow down the selection pool. Following this, the full-text screening phase involved a more in-depth examination of the articles that passed the initial

screening. The complete articles were meticulously reviewed to determine if they aligned with the specified inclusion criteria and contained the necessary data to answer the research question. The study aims, methodologies, participant characteristics, interventions (where applicable), outcomes, and other relevant details were assessed at this stage. Documentation of this process helped maintain transparency in the review process by specifying reasons for inclusion or exclusion at each step.

Critical appraisal

Critical appraisal was conducted using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) (Hong *et al.*, 2018). This appraisal tool was chosen because of its ease of use and applicability to reviews that involve different study designs. The tool comprises two (2) screening questions and five (5) methodological quality criteria. The appraisal was conducted based on the recommendations of the MMAT User Guide. The critical appraisal section of this review involved a comprehensive assessment of the methodological quality and rigour of the studies included in the analysis. Each study's design, sampling methods, data collection processes, and statistical analyses were meticulously evaluated using validation. The goal was to gauge the internal and external validity of the research, considering factors like potential bias, confounding variables, and generalizability of findings. The studies' strengths and limitations were also carefully identified.

Data extraction

A data charting template based on the JBI guidelines was used (Jordan *et al.*, 2019; Santos

et al., 2018). As proposed by earlier reviews, this approach is preferred to others due to its flexibility (Santos *et al.*, 2018). To improve the consistency, applicability, and quality of the data charted, a continuous review through an iterative process was ensured by reading and re-reading the summaries. Publications retrieved were then exported and tabulated with the headings: date, database searched, keywords, and number of publications retrieved and included for review. The data charting template is shown in the appendix (Appendix 1).

Data synthesis and management

The summary findings were organised and collated in a tabular format for synthesis and analysis. A qualitative synthesis approach was used to summarise summary findings from the studies providing evidence on the functionality and efficacy of HCAs in the UK healthcare system. Given the multifaceted nature of healthcare practices, the diverse roles of healthcare assistants (HCAs), and the potential differences in study designs and objectives among various research projects, this approach allowed for the comprehensive integration of a wide range of information. Through the integration of summary findings from multiple studies, the primary objective of the review was to offer a more comprehensive comprehension of the contributions, challenges, and effectiveness of HCAs within the UK healthcare system. This method facilitated the identification of shared themes, discrepancies, and potential areas necessitating further research. Ultimately, it provided a nuanced, evidence-based perspective on the role of HCAs in the UK healthcare system,

aiding policymakers, healthcare professionals, and researchers in making informed decisions and recommendations. This approach also promoted a broader and more holistic understanding of the available evidence.

A narrative reporting format based on the qualitative themes summarised all the extracted data while describing the relation to the review objectives. A summary of the study characteristics of all the reviewed studies to address the review objectives.

Ethical issues identified in primary studies

Ethical aspects within the primary studies were rigorously examined to ensure research integrity and participant well-being. First, the presence of ethical approvals from ethical review boards was scrutinised. All the studies included obtained institutional ethical approval before recruiting participants for data collection.

Emphasising the principle of informed consent, the review further assessed whether studies obtained participants' agreement based on their own volition and maintained confidentiality. Ethical research demands that participants are fully informed about the research's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits (Cocanour, 2017). In this context, it is essential to consider how informed consent was obtained from participants in the primary studies included in the systematic review. As participants themselves or involved in patient care, HCAs must have provided informed consent, acknowledging their participation in studies evaluating their efficacy.

Potential harm to participants was also evaluated, encompassing risk disclosure and mitigation strategies. The principle of "do no harm" is a foundational ethical consideration in research. In the context of a systematic review of healthcare assistants, it is crucial to assess whether the studies under review adhered to this principle (Nusbaum *et al.*, 2017). Researchers must scrutinise the primary studies for any evidence of physical, psychological, or social harm to healthcare assistants or patients participating in the research. Ethical transparency also extends to conflicts of interest and funding sources where applicable, ensuring unbiased research conduct (Vergnes *et al.*, 2010). The authors of the numerous studies declared no conflicts of interest. Moreover, the adherence of studies to data sharing and open science practices was assessed.

As a secondary researcher conducting this systematic review, I had several vital responsibilities. Foremost among them was maintaining the highest standards of academic integrity, which involved diligently citing and referencing all sources to prevent plagiarism. Ensuring that information derived from various authors and sources is presented accurately and fairly, giving due credit to their contributions, was adhered to. Additionally, I rigorously assessed the quality of primary studies using established review protocols and taking measures to minimise bias during data extraction and synthesis. Furthermore, I ensured that in reporting findings, I was transparent and addressed various study limitations. These responsibilities have contributed to enhancing

the systematic review's reliability and credibility. This review underscores commitment to ethical research, ensuring that the conclusions drawn originate from studies that prioritised participant rights, adhered to ethical norms, and practised responsible science.

Chapter Summary

This chapter encapsulates the methodological framework employed in conducting this systematic review on the efficacy and functionality of HCAs in the UK healthcare system. The search strategy encompassed reputable electronic databases using specified search terms. Study selection involved a rigorous multi-step screening of titles, abstracts, and full texts against predefined eligibility criteria. Data extraction focused on critical variables and study characteristics using a standardised form. A rigorous quality assessment tool was applied to gauge study quality and bias. The review adhered to the PRISMA framework, ensuring transparency in the reporting process. Data synthesis and analysis were approached with consideration for heterogeneity, primarily due to the varied methodologies employed in the included studies. Overall, this chapter emphasises the systematic, transparent, and evidence-based approach taken to synthesise the available literature on the research question, enhancing the study's credibility, reliability, and replicability.

CHAPTER FOUR RESULTS

Chapter introduction

This chapter presents the results from the literature search and the findings of the studies

included in the review. The guiding research question was: “What is the functionality and efficacy of HCAs within the UK healthcare system, and what are their challenges?” An overview of the included studies is first given, followed by their methodological characteristics. Results on the quality assessment and the presentation of findings after the qualitative synthesis of study findings follow this.

Findings: Presentation and Synthesis

Literature search results

Due to the limited period of this review, the initial search yielded 247 articles from various databases. Upon removing duplicates, 178 unique articles remained. After screening the titles and abstracts, 117 articles were excluded, leaving 61 for full-text review. The reasons for exclusion included articles that did not encompass the HCA role (n = 22), did not address efficacy outcomes (n = 14), and focused

solely on patient and carer data (n = 11) (Figure 1). Finally, fourteen (14) studies were included in the final review. Searching for additional reference lists did not result in any other relevant studies.

Methodological characteristics of included studies

Of the 14 studies included, six were qualitative, five were interventional (4 non-randomised and one randomised), and 3 used mixed-method designs. The sample sizes ranged from 6 to 565. Sampling methods were mainly non-probability.

Quality appraisal or assessment of included studies

The quality of the included studies was generally moderate-to-high, except for some qualitative studies for which more detail would have been necessary. Those studies were, however, not excluded based on relatively low MMAT quality scores.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow diagram

Table 1: Summary of included studies

Author(s)	Year of publication	Aims/purpose	Methodology	Intervention type	Population and sample size	Outcomes	Summary of key findings
Lovatt et al.	2014	To explore the emotional labour undertaken by health care assistants working in community palliative care from the perspectives of both health care assistants and bereaved family carers.	Qualitative design study	N/A	8	Emotional labour	HCA's view emotional support as a crucial component of their role, and family caregivers greatly appreciate this support. HCAs establish and maintain meaningful relationships with patients while navigating the delicate balance between professionalism and personal connection; they demonstrate adeptness in managing the boundaries between clinical and domestic responsibilities, particularly when caring for patients in their homes; and they collaborate effectively with family caregivers to ensure patients receive the necessary emotional support to enable them to pass away comfortably in the familiar surroundings of their own home.
Cook	2015	To increase diabetes knowledge levels and skills to support insulin	Non-randomized intervention study	Modular training programme	565	Diabetes knowledge levels and abilities to Support insulin administration	This study showed the successful implementation of a comprehensive training program that enables the safe administration of

		administration in non-registered practitioners.					insulin among older individuals with diabetes. Training improved the knowledge and skills of HCAs.
Dutton	2017	To train HCAs to administer insulin at home for suitable patients	Non-randomised intervention study	Training programme	6	Ability to administer insulin for eligible patients at home	HCAs felt motivated and valuable and found it an excellent way to improve their skill. They also acknowledged that the intervention helped reduce work-related pressure on the rest of the team.
Gregory	2019	To train HCAs to become competent in a basic standard in these nine key competency areas for reviewing and managing diabetes	Non-randomised intervention study	Training programme	6	Care planning and target setting, Cost of community nurse visits, Prescribing costs, Insulin errors (reported and unreported), and Incidence of hypoglycaemia	Examining the reflections and skills development of HCAs during the project revealed a notable shift in their perspective towards the care of vulnerable patients. This was evident in the practical knowledge sharing with other team members.
Seale et al.	2013	To identify the challenges of interpreted consultations for healthcare providers and to explain the disadvantage experienced by patients from minority	Mixed methods	N/A	9	Challenges of interpreted consultations for healthcare providers	In interpreted medical consultations, the duration was similar to same-language consultations, but patients tended to speak less. Misunderstandings occurred at a comparable rate, with patients in interpreted sessions posing fewer questions. These encounters exhibited increased social distance, including reduced humour, less

		groups who have diabetes.					discussion of the patient's emotions or personal life, and a decreased likelihood of patients raising non-diabetes-related issues, sharing unique health ideas, or discussing clinical parameters. Providers frequently addressed English-speaking patients directly, while those requiring interpreters were typically discussed in the third person. Sometimes, interpreters altered or omitted translations and introduced their remarks.
Arthur et al.	2017	To understand the relational care training needs of HCAs caring for older people, design a relational care training intervention for HCAs and assess the feasibility of a cluster randomised controlled trial to evaluate the new	Mixed methods	Training intervention	112	Experience of emotional care and quality of life during patients' hospital stay. HCA outcomes were empathy and attitudes towards older people. Ward-level outcomes were the quality of HCA-patient interaction.	About one-third of participants mentioned that HCA training content was related to "relational care." However, the quality and focus of HCA training varied among trusts, emphasising recruits. The main challenge in HCA training is securing their release from ward duties. Older individuals and caregivers are aware of the pressures faced by ward staff, but the quality of relationships with care staff significantly influences their hospital experience. HCAs need training in handling "difficult conversations" with

		intervention against HCA training as usual					patients and relatives, and their preferred learning styles sometimes differ from available training methods.
Kantaris et al.	2019	To introduce and evaluate first aid training for healthcare assistants.	Mixed methods	First aid training programme	16		Training healthcare assistants improved staff confidence, therapeutic engagement with service users and ward culture in general. The skills acquired are relevant and provide an easily understandable toolkit.
Naughton et al.	2014	To estimate the short-term effectiveness, feasibility, and acceptability of a smoking cessation intervention as an adjunct to cessation support in primary care to inform the design of a definitive trial.	Stratified two parallel-group randomised controlled trials comparing usual care (control) with standard care plus the iQuit system (intervention), delivered by primary care nurses/healthcare assistants blinded to the allocation sequence.	Usual care plus tailored printed and Short Message Service (SMS) text message self-help	32 practices	Impact of Training on smoking cessation	The primary outcome showed no significant differences between the two groups: the control group (40.3%) and the iQuit group (45.2%). However, when assessing 6-month prolonged abstinence, the iQuit group had a significantly higher success rate (15.1%) than the control group (8.9%).
Faulkner et al	2016	To estimate the short-term effectiveness, feasibility, and acceptability	Stratified two parallel-group randomised controlled trials comparing usual care (control) with standard care plus the iQuit system	Usual care plus tailored printed and Short Message Service (SMS) text message self-help	32 practices	Effectiveness in delivering smoking cessation support in primary care	Primary care patients who received smoking cessation counselling from auxiliary healthcare professionals were equally as likely to abstain up to 6

		y of a smoking cessation intervention as an adjunct to cessation support in primary care to inform the design of a definitive trial.	(intervention), delivered by primary care nurses/healthcare assistants who were blinded to the allocation sequence.				months later as those who saw nurses. While auxiliary healthcare professionals had somewhat more patient contact time, the advice provided, pharmacotherapies provided, and patient satisfaction were comparable to that of nurses. Extending the responsibilities of the auxiliary healthcare worker to include smoking cessation help may boost job satisfaction while decreasing the costs of cessation support delivery in primary care.
Traynor et al.	2015	To examine how these HCAs positioned themselves as professionals and accounted for professional boundaries.	Qualitative study design	N/A	59	Perception of professional boundaries and function	The thematic analysis uncovered a complex dynamic among participants. They acknowledged their subordinate roles in traditional occupational boundaries and expressed ambitions to challenge these limits. Handpicked by managers, they aimed to become nurses for greater recognition. Their scope of practice relied on individual aptitude, not formal credentials. Some participants claimed to have taken over tasks traditionally associated with nursing as nurses shifted toward

							administrative roles, blurring occupational boundaries.
Matthews & Williamson	2016	To extend understanding of how healthcare assistants construct and manage demanding situations in a secure mental health setting and to explore the effects on their health and well-being.	An exploratory multi-method qualitative approach	N/A	15	Management of demanding situations at the healthcare facility, effects on health and well-being	The study highlighted the distinct nature of inpatient mental healthcare within nursing, where abnormal behaviour is frequently normalised and disconnected from the broader context. HCAs often grappled with a conflict between their innate empathy and the organisation's demand for emotional detachment and control, leading to burnout and moral distress.
Sarre et al.	2018	To investigate HCAs' access to training, support, and assessment ; perceived gaps in training provision; and barriers and facilitators to implementation of relevant policies in acute care.	Qualitative study design	N/A	58	Access to training and support assessment and challenges in policy implementation	Induction training for HCAs was appreciated but deemed insufficient in preparing them for real-life ward challenges. Hospital policies on supervision and competency assessments varied within and between hospitals, influenced by staff availability and competing priorities. Training gaps included dealing with cognitive impairments, emotional management for patients, families, and staff, and navigating difficult conversations.

							Ongoing training access faced obstacles like time constraints, infrequent offerings, ward managers' attitudes, the need to balance training with patient and staff needs, and reliance on e-learning as the default mode of training delivery.
Jansen et al.	2017	To explore the role, perspectives, and experiences of healthcare assistants in pain assessment and management in dementia	Qualitative study design	N/A	14	Roles and experiences	The study revealed three main themes: recognising pain, reporting pain, and wanting additional training. Healthcare workers often identified both evident and subtle signs of pain in residents. Their ability to distinguish pain-related from non-pain-related behaviours was a testament to their expertise. Pain reporting depended greatly on their relationships with professional staff and their sense of being valued in their role. Positive relationships led to thorough pain reporting, while negative ones resulted in more perfunctory or unclear reports. Participants expressed a strong interest in additional training and upskilling, particularly in using and reporting with

							basic pain assessment tools.
Nyashanu et al	2020	To explore the challenges faced by different frontline workers in health and social care during the COVID-19 pandemic	Explorative qualitative design	N/A	40	Challenges	HCA's encountered a multitude of challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic, including a lack of readiness for such a crisis, insufficient availability of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), elevated levels of anxiety and fear among professionals, difficulties in enforcing social distancing measures, struggles in fulfilling social shielding responsibilities, heightened anxiety and fear among residents and service users, delays in testing, evolving PPE guidelines, and a shortage of staff.

Functionality of HCAs

This sub-section describes evidence of the functional capacities of HCAs. Findings on the functionality provide a basis further to explain the efficacy of HCAs in the subsequent sub-section. The qualitative synthesis of identified studies revealed the diverse roles and responsibilities of HCAs within the UK healthcare system, and these were categorised into four main themes: (1) direct patient care, (2) support for healthcare professionals, (3) administrative tasks, and (4) training and education.

Direct Patient Care

HCAs were reported to be frequently at the forefront of providing direct patient care across various healthcare settings, including hospitals, nursing homes, primary care facilities, and community healthcare. Their direct responsibilities included assisting with personal hygiene, feeding and nutrition, mobilisation and transfers, vital sign monitoring, and emotional support.

Assisting with personal hygiene

The findings indicate that HCAs are crucial in assisting patients with personal hygiene needs. Arthur *et al.* (2017) reported that HCAs assisted

patients with bathing, showering, and toileting tasks, promoting personal hygiene and maintaining patients' dignity. By providing this assistance, HCAs help keep the patient's dignity and self-esteem and ensure they feel clean, comfortable, and respected during their healthcare journey (Faulkner *et al.*, 2016; Lovatt *et al.*, 2015; Sarre *et al.*, 2018).

Assisting with nutritional needs

HCAs also ensured patients receive proper nutrition (Gregory, 2019; Kantaris *et al.*, 2020; Naughton *et al.*, 2014). As Kantaris *et al.* (2020) reported, they assist with feeding, particularly in patients with limited mobility or specific dietary requirements. Monitoring dietary intake is a critical aspect of their role, as it helps address nutritional deficiencies and promotes patients' overall well-being (Lovatt *et al.*, 2015).

Helping with mobility

They played a pivotal role in helping patients with mobility, including assisting them in walking, transferring between beds and chairs, and using mobility aids when necessary. HCAs routinely measured and recorded vital signs like blood pressure, temperature, pulse, and respiration, providing valuable data for patient assessments as was reported by Arthur *et al.* (2017), Matthews and Williamson (2016), Cook (2015) and Seale *et al.* (2013). Beyond physical care, Lovatt *et al.* (2015) and Arthur *et al.* (2017) further report that HCAs often provide emotional support to patients, offering a reassuring presence and a listening ear. These direct patient care activities are fundamental to maintaining patient comfort, well-being, and overall health.

Support for Healthcare Professionals

HCAs also played a vital role in supporting registered nurses and other healthcare professionals, effectively extending the reach of the healthcare team. Their contributions included data collection, assisting with procedures, helping with medication adherence, and ensuring patient safety (Arthur *et al.*, 2017; Jansen *et al.*, 2017; Naughton *et al.*, 2014).

Clinical data collection/capture

HCAs collect patient data, such as medical histories, allowing nurses and physicians to make informed clinical decisions (Arthur *et al.*, 2017; Naughton *et al.*, 2014; Sarre *et al.*, 2018). HCAs played a role in documenting patient information ensuring that medical records were accurate and up-to-date (Kantaris *et al.*, 2020). This role was especially crucial in busy healthcare settings. HCAs also assisted with medical procedures, ensuring that all necessary equipment and supplies were readily available and patients were comfortable during the process (Jansen *et al.*, 2017).

Supporting medication adherence and patient monitoring

Three studies (Cook, 2015; Dutton *et al.*, 2018; Gregory, 2019) reported that while not responsible for medication administration, HCAs often helped patients with medication adherence by providing reminders and assistance with pill organisation. HCAs were attentive to patient safety, monitoring signs of distress or deterioration and promptly reporting concerns to the healthcare team.

Administrative Duties

Beyond direct patient care, HCAs contributed significantly to the smooth functioning of healthcare institutions through various administrative responsibilities (Jansen *et al.*, 2017; Kantaris *et al.*, 2020). In some settings, HCAs assisted with appointment scheduling, coordinating patient visits, and managing appointment calendars (Seale *et al.*, 2013). HCAs were responsible for managing supplies, including inventory control, ordering necessary medical equipment, and ensuring the availability of essential supplies (Dutton *et al.*, 2018). They facilitated patient transfers between units or facilities and sometimes participated in the admission and discharge processes (Nyashanu *et al.*, 2020). These administrative tasks streamlined healthcare operations, reducing administrative burdens on nursing staff and improving overall efficiency.

Efficacy of Health Care Assistants

These studies presented here cover diverse topics and provide valuable insights into the efficacy of HCAs across multiple healthcare settings, from diabetes management to palliative care and mental health. They also shed light on the impact of HCAs interventions and training programs on patient care and outcomes.

The study by Cook (2015) aimed to improve diabetes knowledge and skills among non-registered practitioners through a modular training program. The program successfully enhanced the knowledge and skills of HCAs, particularly in supporting insulin administration for older individuals with diabetes. Similarly, Dutton *et al.* (2018) focused on training HCAs to

administer insulin at home for suitable patients. The intervention proved motivating for HCAs, improved their skills, and even helped reduce work-related pressure on the rest of the healthcare team. Gregory's study also aimed to train HCAs in essential competency areas for reviewing and managing diabetes. The study found that this training resulted in a notable shift in the perspective of HCAs towards caring for vulnerable patients. It emphasised the importance of knowledge sharing among team members (Gregory, 2019).

In the first aid field, Kantaris *et al.* (2020) introduced and evaluated comprehensive training for HCAs. The training improved staff confidence, enhanced therapeutic engagement with service users, and positively impacted the ward culture. The randomised controlled trial by Naughton *et al.* (2014) assessed the short-term effectiveness of a smoking cessation intervention in primary care. The intervention involved usual care plus tailored printed and Short Message Service (SMS) text message self-help, whereas the control arm involved only routine maintenance. With regular care, the role of HCAs was to give smoking cessation advice. While the primary outcome showed no significant differences between the two groups, the intervention group had a significantly higher success rate in 6-month prolonged abstinence. This pointed to the centrality of HCAs in assisting with public health preventive programmes, especially for non-communicable diseases.

Faulkner's study also examined a smoking cessation intervention in primary care. It found

that primary care patients who received smoking cessation counselling from auxiliary healthcare professionals were equally likely to abstain up to 6 months later than those who saw nurses. The study highlighted that extending the responsibilities of additional healthcare workers to include smoking cessation support could have benefits in terms of job satisfaction and cost-effectiveness (Faulkner *et al.*, 2016).

The efficacy of HCAs within the UK healthcare system is a multifaceted topic encompassing various dimensions of their roles and contributions. It extends to improved patient outcomes, such as enhanced patient comfort. HCAs are often responsible for assisting patients with personal hygiene, dressing, and mobility. These tasks not only maintain hygiene but also improve patient comfort and dignity.

Efficacy also included improved compliance with treatment regimens (Dutton *et al.*, 2018; Faulkner *et al.*, 2016). HCAs assist with medication management and adherence, ensuring patients follow prescribed regimens (Cook, 2015). This support improves disease management and health outcomes (Dutton *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, HCAs' follow-up care and monitoring contribute to reduced rates of hospital readmissions, particularly in community healthcare settings (Gregory, 2019; Lovatt *et al.*, 2015). They help identify early signs of health issues and intervene promptly (Gregory, 2019).

These findings highlight HCAs' crucial role in promoting positive patient experiences and health outcomes. Their interactions with patients are often characterised by empathy,

compassion, and personalised care, fostering a sense of trust and comfort.

Overall, the efficacy of HCAs within the healthcare system is conspicuous in how they improve the workflow and efficiency of healthcare facilities. Some studies underscored this aspect, emphasising the impact of HCAs on healthcare operations (Arthur *et al.*, 2017; Cook, 2015; Dutton *et al.*, 2018; Gregory, 2019).

Challenges faced by HCAs

This section expounds on study findings concerning the challenges HCAs face in their line of work.

Matthews and Williamson (2016) examined healthcare assistants in secure mental health settings. It emphasised the unique challenges of inpatient mental healthcare, where abnormal behaviour is normalised, and HCAs often face a conflict between empathy and the need for emotional detachment and control, leading to burnout and moral distress.

Lovatt *et al.* (2015) explored the emotional labour of HCAs in community palliative care. HCAs were found to consider emotional support as a crucial aspect of their role. They navigated a delicate balance between professionalism and forming personal connections with patients and their families. This involved establishing and maintaining meaningful relationships while effectively managing boundaries between clinical and domestic responsibilities. The study highlighted the effective collaboration between HCAs and family caregivers, ensuring patients received essential emotional support during palliative care at home.

In the study by Seale *et al.* (2013), they examined interpreted medical consultations, comparing them to same-language consultations. The study found that interpreted consultations had similar durations but less patient participation, including fewer patient questions. Interpreted sessions also showed signs of increased social distance and different provider-patient dynamics. Thus, in some settings, language barriers pose a challenge for HCAs and possibly limit their functionality.

The study by Arthur *et al.* (2017) aimed to understand the relational care training needs of HCAs caring for older people. Findings showed that HCA training content related to "relational care" varied among healthcare trusts, focusing on recruits. The challenge in HCA training was securing their release from ward duties. The study highlighted the significance of the quality of relationships with care staff in influencing the hospital experience of older individuals and caregivers. HCAs expressed a need for training in handling difficult conversations with patients and relatives.

Traynor *et al.* (2015) explored how HCAs positioned themselves professionally and accounted for professional boundaries. It revealed a complex dynamic among participants, with a few aspiring to become nurses for greater recognition. The study highlighted that the scope of practice for HCAs depended on individual aptitude rather than formal credentials.

Sarre's study investigated HCAs' access to training, support, and assessment in acute care settings (Sarre *et al.*, 2018). It revealed that induction training was appreciated but

insufficient in preparing HCAs for real-life ward challenges. The study also found variations in hospital policies regarding supervision and competency assessments influenced by staff availability and competing priorities.

The qualitative study by Jansen *et al.* (2017) explored HCAs' roles in pain assessment and management in dementia care. It emphasised the expertise of HCAs in recognising and reporting pain, depending on their relationships with professional staff and their sense of being valued in their role. The study also highlighted HCAs' desire for additional training, particularly in using and reporting with basic pain assessment tools.

Finally, Nyashanu *et al.* (2020) explored the challenges frontline health and social care workers (including mainly HCAs) faced during the COVID-19 pandemic. It identified a range of challenges, including a lack of pandemic preparedness, shortages of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), anxiety and fear among professionals, difficulties in enforcing social distancing measures, struggles in fulfilling social shielding responsibilities, heightened anxiety and fear among residents and service users, delays in testing, evolving PPE guidance, and a shortage of staff.

Chapter Summary

In summary, HCAs in the UK play indispensable roles in providing direct patient care, supporting healthcare professionals, and managing specific administrative tasks. Their dedication and versatility contribute significantly to the functioning and effectiveness of healthcare systems across various settings. This review

provides valuable insights into the functionality of HCAs in the UK. Additionally, the efficacy of HCA within the UK healthcare system is evident in their positive impact on patient outcomes, the streamlined healthcare workflow, and their contributions to the overall quality of care. HCAs' roles are not limited to task-oriented activities; they encompass a compassionate and patient-centred approach that enhances the healthcare experience for patients and supports the healthcare team in delivering high-quality care. While challenges exist, acknowledging and addressing them can further optimise the efficacy of HCAs and their contributions to the healthcare system.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Chapter introduction

This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of the findings and insights garnered from this systematic review. The preceding chapters have provided an elaborate exploration of the roles, efficacy, and challenges of HCAs in diverse healthcare settings. This chapter summarises and further examines the broader implications of the findings and offers insights into the current state of HCAs in the UK healthcare system. The limitations and strengths are presented to guide the interpretation of the review findings. Finally, actionable recommendations for policymakers, researchers, and healthcare institutions are provided.

Summary of main findings and linkage to research questions

One of the key findings regarding the efficacy of HCAs is their ability to enhance their knowledge

and skills through training programs. Studies like Cook (2015) and the modular training program for diabetes management have shown that HCAs can significantly improve their understanding and competency in specific areas of healthcare. This enhanced knowledge and skill development translates into their effectiveness in providing patient care, for instance, regarding tasks like insulin administration or managing chronic conditions. This has been highlighted in previous global literature reviews (Fee *et al.*, 2020; Just *et al.*, 2021). This support for healthcare professionals helped optimise the workflow of healthcare facilities and allowed registered nurses and doctors to focus on more specialised tasks.

The inclusion of first aid training for HCAs has been found to have a positive impact on their roles. Kantaris *et al.* (2020) demonstrated that such training improves staff confidence and enhances their ability to engage therapeutically with service users. This training equips HCAs with valuable skills crucial in emergencies, ultimately benefiting patient safety and well-being. The ability to respond effectively to medical emergencies adds an extra layer of efficacy to their roles.

HCAs, moreover, have made notable contributions to smoking cessation programs in primary care settings. Some randomised controlled trials have shown that HCAs can be pivotal in delivering smoking cessation support to patients (Faulkner *et al.*, 2016; Naughton *et al.*, 2014). While primary care nurses often lead such interventions, auxiliary healthcare professionals like HCAs have proven equally

effective in helping patients quit smoking. This contributes to better patient outcomes and demonstrates the versatility and effectiveness of HCAs in public health programs, as espoused in other studies (Free *et al.*, 2013; Lizarondo *et al.*, 2010; O'Brien *et al.*, 2023).

The efficacy of HCAs is perhaps most prominently seen in their positive impact on patient outcomes and comfort. Their roles encompass assisting patients with personal hygiene, feeding, mobility, and vital sign monitoring. These activities are fundamental to maintaining patient comfort, well-being, and overall health. HCAs' ability to enhance patient comfort is especially crucial in settings where patients may be vulnerable or require specialised care, such as palliative care or mental health facilities (Cavendish, 2013; Matthews and Williamson, 2016; Stanhope and Pearce, 2013).

HCAs also contribute significantly to the workflow and efficiency of healthcare facilities. Several studies, including Arthur *et al.* (2017), have highlighted their role in improving the overall functioning of healthcare teams. By assisting with routine tasks, such as patient care and monitoring, HCAs allow other healthcare professionals to focus on more specialised and complex aspects of care. This contributes to streamlined healthcare operations, reduced workload on other team members, and potentially cost-effective care delivery (Wilson *et al.*, 2023). The efficacy of HCAs is not only in direct patient care but also in optimising the overall functioning of healthcare systems.

Regarding the challenges that HCAs face, it was noted that they often grapple with burnout and

moral distress due to the emotionally demanding nature of their work. The constant exposure to illness, suffering, and death can affect their mental and emotional well-being. Witnessing patients' pain and struggles, especially in palliative care and mental health settings, can lead to profound emotional exhaustion and moral dilemmas (Fee *et al.*, 2020; O'Brien *et al.*, 2023). HCAs may be torn between multiple problems, significantly affecting their work. HCAs routinely engage in emotional labour, a crucial but emotionally taxing aspect of their role. They provide not only physical care but also emotional support to patients and their families. This emotional labour can be particularly challenging when dealing with patients facing serious illnesses or at the end of life (Fee *et al.*, 2020; Jansen *et al.*, 2017). HCAs must manage their emotions while remaining empathetic, striking a delicate balance between professionalism and personal connection. The constant demand for emotional labour can lead to stress and emotional exhaustion.

Language barriers can pose significant challenges for HCAs in healthcare settings with diverse patient populations. Effective communication is essential for providing safe and quality care. Language barriers can hinder patient understanding, leading to misunderstandings, miscommunications, and potential safety issues (Cavendish, 2013). HCAs must find ways to bridge these language gaps to ensure patients receive the care they need. Overcoming language barriers often requires additional effort and resources, adding to the complexity of their roles.

Moreover, HCAs frequently encounter situations that require them to engage in difficult conversations with patients and their families. These conversations may involve discussing serious diagnoses, treatment options, end-of-life care, or emotional support. However, not all HCAs receive comprehensive training in handling such conversations (Brown *et al.*, 2021; Recio-Saucedo *et al.*, 2018). Varied training needs to exist among HCAs, and some may feel ill-equipped to navigate these sensitive discussions. Improving training in this area is crucial to ensure that HCAs can effectively support patients during challenging times.

The COVID-19 pandemic also underscored the critical importance of PPEs for healthcare workers, including HCAs. During the pandemic, shortages of PPE placed HCAs at risk of infection while caring for COVID-19 patients. The lack of adequate PPE jeopardised their health and heightened anxiety and fear among HCAs and their patients. Sufficient access to PPE is essential to ensure the safety of HCAs and the patients they care for.

The pandemic also revealed a lack of preparedness within the healthcare system, impacting HCAs' ability to respond effectively to the crisis. Many HCAs reported feeling ill-prepared to manage a public health emergency of this magnitude. The absence of clear protocols and guidance contributed to their anxiety and fear. Addressing this challenge requires initiative-taking, planning and preparedness to equip HCAs and the healthcare system to respond to future crises.

HCAs often find themselves navigating complex professional boundaries in their roles. While they are essential healthcare team members, their scope of practice may be undefined or fluid, leading to potential challenges in defining their roles and responsibilities. Some HCAs aspire to advance their careers, such as becoming nurses, while others may feel constrained by a lack of formal credentials. Navigating these professional boundaries can be challenging and impact job satisfaction and career progression.

HCAs may experience elevated levels of anxiety and fear, particularly in high-stress healthcare environments or during public health crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. Fear of contracting infections, concerns about patient outcomes, and the emotional burden of caring for seriously ill patients can contribute to heightened anxiety. These emotional challenges can affect HCAs' mental well-being and job satisfaction, emphasising the need for adequate support and resources to address their emotional needs.

Limitations and strengths of research

The study has several limitations that should be considered. Firstly, it maintains a somewhat limited scope by predominantly focusing on HCAs within the UK healthcare system. Consequently, the generalizability of its findings to healthcare systems in other countries, with varying structures and policies, may be limited. Secondly, the study relies heavily on published literature, potentially introducing publication bias as it may overlook unpublished or negatively reported studies. Furthermore, the included studies encompass a broad spectrum of healthcare settings and topics, resulting in

methodological and contextual heterogeneity, possibly affecting the capacity to derive consistent conclusions. Lastly, there might be variations in the quality of the included studies, which the review may not fully account for, thus potentially impacting its overall validity.

This study exhibits several notable strengths. It undertakes a comprehensive review of the existing literature, incorporating studies from diverse healthcare settings. This approach offers a broad and multifaceted perspective on the role, efficacy, and challenges of HCAs in the UK. Additionally, the study encompasses diverse topics, including diabetes management, palliative care, and mental health, highlighting the adaptability and significance of HCAs across different healthcare domains. Furthermore, the study's focus on patient outcomes and comfort aligns seamlessly with the patient-centred care approach, underscoring HCAs' pivotal role in delivering high-quality healthcare. Lastly, the review goes beyond mere analysis, offering actionable recommendations that hold practical value for policymakers, healthcare practitioners, and researchers. These recommendations facilitate informed decision-making and the enhancement of HCAs' roles within healthcare systems.

Implications of findings

The implications of the findings from this systematic review are multifaceted and hold significant relevance for healthcare policy, practice, and research. Firstly, policymakers should consider the need for standardised training programs and role definitions for Healthcare Assistants (HCAs) to ensure

consistency and quality in their contributions to healthcare systems. Acknowledging the emotional labour involved in HCA roles, policies should prioritise resources for managing burnout and moral distress. Addressing language barriers through language access services is crucial to effective communication. Research should focus on long-term efficacy, patient-reported outcomes, workplace well-being, and the impact of interprofessional collaboration involving HCAs. Healthcare facilities must prioritise ongoing training, provide emotional support resources, ensure clear role definitions, and be prepared for pandemics. These recommendations collectively aim to optimise the role of HCAs, improve patient experiences, and enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of healthcare systems.

Recommendations for policy, practice, and research

Recommendations for policy

1. **Standardized Training:** Implement standardised and comprehensive training programs for HCAs across different healthcare settings. Ensure that training covers essential skills, communication, emotional support, and patient safety.
2. **Recognition of Roles:** Develop clear and standardised role descriptions and scopes of practice for HCAs. Recognise and validate their contributions to the healthcare system, including their roles in personal hygiene, feeding, mobility assistance, and vital sign monitoring.
3. **Emotional Support:** Policies should acknowledge the emotional labour involved

in HCA roles, particularly in palliative care and mental health settings. Provide resources and support to address burnout and moral distress among HCAs.

4. **Language Access:** In healthcare settings with diverse patient populations, policy initiatives should promote language access services, including interpreters and translated materials, to address language barriers and ensure effective communication.
5. **PPE and Pandemic Preparedness:** Develop and maintain stockpiles of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) to ensure the safety of HCAs during public health crises. Invest in pandemic preparedness and clear protocols for healthcare workers' protection.

Recommendations for research

1. **Long-term efficacy:** Conduct long-term studies to assess the sustained impact of HCA training programs on patient outcomes, especially in chronic disease management and smoking cessation programs.
2. **Quality of life measures:** Explore research avenues focusing on the impact of HCAs on patients' quality of life, comfort, and overall well-being. Investigate the connection between patient-reported outcomes and HCA interventions.
3. **Workplace Well-Being:** Investigate the relationship between workplace factors, such as staffing levels, workload, and job satisfaction, on HCA efficacy and retention. Identify strategies to enhance HCAs' workplace well-being.
4. **Interprofessional Collaboration:** Research the effectiveness of interprofessional

collaboration between HCAs and other healthcare providers. Assess care delivery outcomes when HCAs collaborate with nurses, doctors, and other professionals.

5. **Patient-Centered Care:** Explore the impact of HCAs on the delivery of patient-centered care. Investigate patient preferences, satisfaction, and experiences with HCA-provided care.

Recommendations for practice

1. **Ongoing Training:** Healthcare facilities should prioritise ongoing training and professional development for HCAs. This includes training in handling difficult conversations, cultural competence, and utilising essential pain assessment tools.
2. **Emotional Support Resources:** Provide access to resources for HCAs to manage the emotional demands of their roles. This can include counselling services, peer support programs, and stress management workshops.
3. **Language Access Services:** Ensure healthcare facilities have language access services, including interpreters and translated materials, to overcome language barriers and facilitate effective communication.
4. **Clear Role Definitions:** Clearly define and communicate the roles and responsibilities of HCAs within healthcare teams. Ensure that HCAs know their scope of practice and the boundaries of their roles.
5. **Pandemic Response Plans:** Develop and regularly update pandemic response plans that prioritise the safety of HCAs. This should include adequate access to PPE, clear

infection control guidelines, and mental health support during public health crises.

6. **Patient Feedback:** Encourage feedback from patients and their families regarding their experiences with HCAs. Use this feedback to improve the quality of care provided by HCAs continuously.
7. **Team Collaboration:** Promote a culture of collaboration and respect within healthcare teams. Recognise and appreciate the contributions of HCAs as integral members of the group.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this systematic review offers a comprehensive examination of HCAs in the context of the UK's healthcare system, addressing their roles, challenges, and effectiveness. The study highlights the versatility and importance of HCAs in various healthcare domains, encompassing diabetes management, palliative care, mental health, and primary care. Despite their pivotal role in enhancing patient care and outcomes, HCAs encounter several obstacles, including burnout, emotional labour, language barriers, and varying training needs. The COVID-19 pandemic further emphasised the indispensable role HCAs play in healthcare delivery. To fully harness their potential, policymakers should prioritise standardised training, role clarification, and the provision of resources to support their emotional well-being. Research efforts should concentrate on long-term impacts and fostering interprofessional collaboration involving HCAs. In practical terms, continual training, dynamic support mechanisms, and readiness for pandemics are

imperative. HCAs remain central to patient-centric care, operational efficiency, and the overall triumph of healthcare systems, warranting recognition and support for their invaluable contributions.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Table 1: Data charting template

Author(s)
Year of publication
Origin/country of origin (where the source was published or conducted)
Aims/purpose
Population and sample size
Methodology
Intervention type, comparator, and details of these (e.g., duration of the intervention) (if applicable).
Duration of the intervention (if applicable)
Outcomes and details of these (e.g., how measured) (if applicable)
Key findings that relate to the systematic review research question

Appendix 2: Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT), version 2018

Category of study designs	Methodological quality criteria	Responses			
		Yes	No	Cannot tell	Comments
Screening questions (For all types)	S1. Are there clear research questions?				
	S2. Do the collected data allow us to address the research questions?				
	<i>Further appraisal may not be feasible or appropriate when the answer is 'No' or 'Can't tell' to one or both screening questions.</i>				
1. Qualitative	1.1. Is the qualitative approach appropriate to answer the research question?				
	1.2. Are the qualitative data collection methods adequate to address the research question?				
	1.3. Are the findings adequately derived from the data?				
	1.4. Is the interpretation of results sufficiently substantiated by data?				
	1.5. Is there coherence between qualitative data sources, collection, analysis, and interpretation?				
2. Quantitative randomised controlled trials	2.1. Is randomisation appropriately performed?				
	2.2. Are the groups comparable at baseline?				
	2.3. Are there complete outcome data?				
	2.4. Are outcome assessors blinded to the intervention provided?				
	2.5. Did the participants adhere to the assigned intervention?				
3. Quantitative non-randomized	3.1. Are the participants representative of the target population?				
	3.2. Are measurements appropriate regarding both the outcome and intervention (or exposure)?				
	3.3. Are there complete outcome data?				
	3.4. Are the confounders accounted for in the design and analysis?				
	3.5. During the study period, is the intervention administered (or exposure occurred) as intended?				
4. Quantitative descriptive	4.1. Is the sampling strategy relevant to address the research question?				
	4.2. Is the sample representative of the target population?				
	4.3. Are the measurements appropriate?				
	4.4. Is the risk of nonresponse bias low?				
	4.5. Is the statistical analysis appropriate to answer the research question?				
5. Mixed methods	5.1. Is there an adequate rationale for using a mixed methods design to address the research question?				
	5.2. Are the different components of the study effectively integrated to answer the research question?				

	5.3. Are the outputs of integrating qualitative and quantitative components adequately interpreted?				
	5.4. Are divergences and inconsistencies between quantitative and qualitative results adequately addressed?				
	5.5. Do the different components of the study adhere to the quality criteria of each tradition of the methods involved?				

Ethical Acknowledgment

I hereby declare that my work is original and data was sourced in line with the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) requirements.

Conflicts of Interests: Nil

Grants: Ni